

DEVELOPMENT OF AN EXPANDED STRUCTURE FOR MANAGING INFORMATION FLOWS IN SMART LIVESTOCK FARMS

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Abstract. Today, the construction of diagnostic models based on the theory of fuzzy logic algorithms and neutrosophic fuzzy sets, the classification of poorly formed processes is a developing direction. However, the diagnosis and analysis of the causes of the spread of animal disease with the introduction of modern information technologies require further improvement. The developed algorithms and software allow to increase the economic efficiency of diagnosis and prognosis of the disease based on the statistical data of the regional department of veterinary medicine and livestock development.

Keywords: in smart livestock farms, algorithm, fuzzy set theory, IDEF0 process.

Currently, great attention is paid to the automation of all aspects. One of the convenient means of automation is the use of computer technology. The widespread use of computers allows you to automate the work processes of representatives of the veterinary profession. Introduction of digital technologies in organizations subordinate to district (city) departments and offices.

Based on this, the consistent implementation of measures to expand domestic opportunities in livestock farming, in particular large-scale cattle breeding, which is considered an important pillar of the "Digital Economy" in our country, and the

systematic practical assistance provided by the state are creating an opportunity to increase the number of livestock and fill domestic consumer markets with livestock products [1].

According to statistical data in our country, in 2023, livestock farms of all categories produced 2,833.3 thousand tons of meat in live weight, 11,968.7 thousand tons of milk, 8,487.5 million eggs, 38.6 thousand tons of wool, 1,321.1 thousand karakul skins, and 198.9 thousand tons of fish were caught, which is an average increase of 3-4% compared to 2022. If data on livestock production are analyzed by economic category, then for 2022-2023, meat and milk production will account for 6.3% and 5.9% of farms, 84.9% and 92.8% of dehqan and household farms, and 8.8% and 1.3% of organizations carrying out agricultural activities, respectively.

Error detection algorithm based on artificial testing data

This graduation qualification work presents the construction and results of logical-linguistic models in the conditions of appropriate parameters that allow assessing the probability of secondary osteodystrophy among imported and local breeds of cows in the conditions of cattle farms. The model built on the basis of the research is compared with experiments conducted in the Samarkand region. When building predictive models, the theory of fuzzy sets is used, taking into account the identified factors contributing to the development of diseases, based on statistical reports on the results of several experiments.

Using fuzzy set theory, the evaluation and prediction model is implemented by querying the expert system, developing a fuzzy rule in each row "if . . . then . . ." In this case, the expert is given a certain set of values of input linguistic parameters, since it is suitable for diagnosing certain cases.

This approach allows taking into account quantitative and qualitative (verbal) variables and does not require knowledge of special branches of mathematics, leaving the expert to assess the situation only in his professional language. In

In addition, orthogonality based on experimental data ensures the independence and variability of the variables (matrix columns) - the expert's ambiguity in all variables is "similarity", which corresponds to the intuitive knowledge of the specialist and allows them to be formalized in the form of a multiplied model.

In accordance with accepted clinical practice, the main disease is determined. Based on the data provided, a list of diagnoses is compiled and a numerical value is assigned to each diagnosis. When establishing the diagnosis of secondary osteodystrophy, we take into account the following main parameters measured in laboratory conditions:

x₁-Temperature, x₂- Pulse per minute, x₃- Respiration per minute, x₄- Rumination per two minutes, x₅- Red blood cell count million/ μ l, x₆- Hemoglobin g/l, x₇- Total protein g/l, x₈- Total calcium mol/l, x₉- Organic phosphorus mol/l, x₁₀- Glucose mol/l, x₁₁- Alkaline reserve ($[\text{SO}]_{-2}$), x₁₂- Copper mol/l, x₁₃- Cobalt mol/l, x₁₄- Manganese mol/l, x₁₅- Zinc mol/l, x₁₆- Number of infusoria in large intestine, x₁₇- Large intestine fluid [2].

The process of building a fuzzy logic model of assessment and prediction based on experimental data is considered.

In general, the degree of dependence of disease parameters using regression equations is determined by the following formula:

In the decision-making process, one often has to deal with issues of a multi-criteria nature. In this case, the set of criteria is usually of a non-equivalent nature. Forecasting models are used to reduce a set of performance indicators (specific objectives) to a single performance estimate (general objective). That is, a forecasting model is a mechanism for reducing specific objective functions to a generalized objective function.

To build a mathematical model for recommending the dependence of diagnostic symptoms on 17 given (initial study results), it is first necessary to assess how much information is available. 17 types of signs (symptoms) of diseases are

given to identify micronutrient diseases in animals. Based on these materials, it is possible to set the task of creating mathematical models. However, the data in our existing observation materials have a number of significant shortcomings:

The low number of complaints about a particular disease and, for various reasons, insufficient data on the symptoms of this disease.

In the field of information technology, it is a work that provides a solution to a problem on a computer. When the composition, structure, and representation of the necessary information to achieve the set goal are determined, and the connections between them are clearly expressed, the problem is considered to be solved.

The issue of determining the level of microelementosis in cows is an urgent issue. Therefore, any scientifically based methodology for assessing microelementosis is of interest.

The level of microelementosis is a complex indicator that characterizes the disease state of cows and the quality of cow disease management, which is ultimately expressed in its disease equivalent, but is not limited to the consequences of the disease.

The main goal of building an automated management information system for livestock farming is to reduce farm costs and increase the production of quality products. Modeling its business process is an important part of designing an information system, and modeling using the IDEF0 methodology is currently popular and is understandable for stakeholders. The IDEF0 business process has 3 inputs and 1 output (Figure 1) [3].

Figure 1. General diagram of farm information flow management

In particular, in the farm subject area, the upper inputs are various documents, norms and clear immutable laws and information sets describing actions in the process; the lower inputs are objects that do not change their state in the process, such as people, sensors and external systems; the right inputs are animal data, records, journals, feed and breeding, such as basic material resources. Also, the output of the process is the resulting information, such as decisions, forecasts and reports, formed from the parameters of the inputs [1, 4].

The life cycle of cattle on the farm covers the period from its birth/arrival to its exit from the farm. This includes the periods of sequential transition from the natural physio-biological changes in the life of each individual between the entry and exit boundaries. It is very convenient to use the IDEF0 process diagram to describe the life cycle transition (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Life cycle process diagram of cattle on a farm

The disease detection/prediction block ensures economic and social efficiency in farm activities. In this case, early detection of the disease serves to prevent its serious consequences and spread, save material resources such as medicines caused by the disease, maintain quality products and production indicators, and ensure food demand and safety. Diseases do not immediately manifest themselves clinically, but initially manifest themselves through symptoms of the disease. Identifying these symptoms through human observation or continuous medical examination is a very difficult task. According to the successful results achieved by researchers in the field, animal diseases or biological changes in them are necessarily reflected in activity, movements, behavior, and appearance. However, these symptoms are related to the number of symptoms, the relationships between them, and the correct establishment of patterns. Nowadays, advanced sensor technologies are taking over the accurate and reliable monitoring of disease symptoms, and modern computer algorithms are taking over the diagnosis of disease from a cognitive-experiential perspective.

Figure 3. Extended structure of information flow management

The reason for proposing this management structure is that systems are now moving away from a single computer and expanding. While the components of previous information systems (such as system code, input data source, output data) were concentrated at a single point, current systems are concentrated at many points connected by a network. Such systems are executed sequentially and/or in parallel on distributed nodes. Also, one component of modern systems can be located at many points. For example, the main program modules/algorithms of the system can be executed on different computing servers, data can be stored in different cells of the cloud, output information can be transmitted to different points, and several systems can cooperate in various aspects. For example, the above systems can be used as an example of a large-scale or multi-layered complex computing system to diagnose cattle diseases, predict productivity, and prepare decisions or reports for users on various issues based on data obtained from IoT sensors on a livestock farm. The architecture of this exemplary computing system is illustrated in Figure 3, which mainly consists of two parts: the internal and external environment, i.e. the cloud and the farm.

The system consists of two parts:

1. Control part
2. Monitoring part

Figure 4. Access to the administration section

Here you can make changes to all sections and add users. So far, these operations are performed only by the administrator.

We summarize the advantages of fuzzy expert systems over simple systems, which are manifested in solving complex algorithmic diagnostic problems.

Modern technological solutions provide the patient with free access to medical services regardless of their place of residence, the availability of high-tech medical services significantly increases medical expertise.

The selection of these factors is modeled on the basis of expert, that is, doctor's advice. This model can be widely used in decision-making.

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